

Electrolytic Regeneration of Acidic Dichromate used in Oxidation of Alcohols

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FOR the oxidation of alcohols the common industrial and laboratory practice is to use acidic dichromate¹ or CrO₃. The reduced chromium salt is thrown as waste, thus apart from making the process expensive it also poses pollution problem. Regeneration of dichromate with a chemical oxidant like potassium permanganate is expensive and is not free from pollution. The direct anodic oxidation of alcohols on platinum or PbO₂ affords mixture of products in poor yields. The two-stage process involving the oxidation of alcohols with inorganic oxidants and then reoxidation of the reduced inorganic species electrolytically² appeared to be an attractive alternative. Hence the present investigation was undertaken.

Experimental

The alcohols (Table 1) were of B.D.H. grade. Borneol was prepared from camphor by the known procedure³. Sodium dichromate (L.R.; B.D.H.) and sulphuric acid (A.R.) were used.

General method⁴ of oxidation of alcohols: To a mixture of the alcohol (0.02 mol) and 30% sulphuric acid (20 ml) was added a solution of sodium dichromate (0.02 mol) keeping the temperature at 27–35°, and refluxed for 3 h. The reaction mixture was cooled to the room temperature and the crude product was isolated from it either by filtration or extraction with ether. After the usual work up, the product was purified by recrystallisation or distillation (Table 1). The dark green aqueous layer containing chromous sulphate was collected. A known volume of which was used for the subsequent anodic oxidation to regenerate the reagent.

Electrolytic regeneration of acidic dichromate:

The dark green chromous sulphate solution free from organic contamination was made upto 100 ml with 30% H₂SO₄. The solution was oxidised at lead oxide anode in a divided cell. The conversion of Cr^{III} to Cr^{VI} was estimated iodometrically. The detail of specification is given below: anolyte, 50 ml of acidic chromous sulphate solution; catholyte, 35 ml of 30% H₂SO₄; anode, lead oxide plate (area=0.074 2 dm²); Pb-cathode, 1A (c.d 14.2 A dm⁻²); temp., 30°.

The electrolysis was carried out in a 250 ml beaker cell with chromous sulphate (50 ml) as anolyte and 30% H₂SO₄ (35 ml) as catholyte, separated by a porous clay diaphragm. The anolyte was stirred

magnetically. A current of 1 A was passed for double the calculated time for 3F mol⁻¹. The voltage of the cell varied from 4 to 5 V. On completion of the reaction, the colour of the solution turned from green to orange red. The results are given in Table 2.

Results and Discussion

During the course of the present investigation five alcohols (Table 1) have been oxidised with acidic sodium dichromate. Three alcohols (Sl. nos. 1–3) gave carboxylic acids while the others (Sl. no. 4 and 5), the secondary alcohols, afforded ketones (Table 1). The stoichiometry of the oxidation can be represented by the equations,

Primary alcohol:

Secondary alcohol:

TABLE 1—OXIDATION OF ALCOHOLS WITH ACIDIC Na₂Cr₂O₇·2H₂O

Sl. no.	Alcohol	Product	M.p /B.p ^a (°C) Found/ (lit. 5)	Yield %
1.	Benzyl alcohol	Benzoic acid	121 (121–122)	92.8
2.	Cinnamyl alcohol	Cinnamic acid	130 (133)	38.3
3.	Allyl alcohol	Acrylic acid	140 (141)	32.5
4.	Cyclohexanol	Cyclohexanone	155 (155)	62.9
5.	Borneol	Camphor	178–80 (178–80)	55.6

The Cr³⁺ (normally a waste and pollutant) has been regenerated by its anodic oxidation at lead oxide anode according to the equations.

The percentage of conversion was estimated by titrating Cr^{VI} iodometrically⁶. It is important that the aqueous layer of chromous sulphate should not contaminate any organic material which otherwise being prone to oxidation reduces the efficiency of regeneration to some extent. The effect of current density on the yield and current efficiency is given in Table 2.

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TABLE 2—EFFECT OF C.D. ON REGENERATION OF Cr^{VI}

Sl. no.	Current A	C.d. A dm ²	Cell voltage V	Reaction time (h)		Cr ^{VI} %	C.E. %
				Theoretical	Practical		
1.	0.5	7.14	3	3.1	7.0	78.3	62.9
2.	1.0	14.2	4-5	1.6	3.5	81.3	61.5
3.	1.5	21.4	3-4	1.07	5.0	93.5	71.8

The results of Table 2 indicate that with the increase in current density the conversion of Cr^{III} to Cr^{VI} also increases (max 93.5%; C.E. 71.8%). It has been also observed in a separate experiment that when current is passed for the theoretical time ($3F \text{ mol}^{-1}$), only 20% conversion is achieved. The procedure of regeneration appears to be important in view of the large amount of oxidant used in industries. The result obtained by the oxidation with CrO_3 are quite similar. Here also under the above condition 92% chromic acid is regenerated with 30% current efficiency.

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C-Acylation of *p*-Acetotoluidide in Presence of Polyphosphoric Acid

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SACHA and Patel¹ carried out Friedel-Craft's acylation of different acetanilides, *p*-substitution predominating with respect to the amino group; acylation, however, failed in case of aceto-*p*-toluidide. Desai and Desai² observed *N*-acyl migration

in presence of polyphosphoric acid with different acetanilides in *para*-position to the amino group and also *N*-benzoyl migration. Further, in case of *p*-benzoyltoluidide, 2-hydroxy-4-phenyl-6-methylquinoline was formed, the intermediate ketone getting cyclised

In the present work, aceto-*p*-toluidide, when heated with PPA and acetic anhydride gave not only 2,6-dimethyl-4-hydroxyquinoline (1) but also two ketones, 5-acetamino-2-methylacetophenone (2) and 6-acetamino-3-methylacetophenone (3); the former could be easily obtained, but the latter with difficulty owing to its cyclisation into the corresponding 4-hydroxyquinoline. The formation of 2-hydroxy- or 4-hydroxy-quinoline is due to the cyclodehydration of the corresponding acetamino ketone being formed either due to benzoyl migration (*loc cit*) or to C-acylation of *p*-acetotoluidide (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

Experimental

2,6-Dimethyl-4 hydroxyquinoline : *p*-Toluidine (5 g) converted into acetotoluidide with acetic anhydride was heated with PPA (H_3PO_4 , 25 ml; P_2O_5 , 40 g) at 170° for 4.5 h. After cooling, the mass was neutralised on acidic side giving precipitate, which after removal, was extracted with ethylacetate, the extract product being identified as *p*-acetotoluidide.

On basifying PPA solution, the product obtained was crystallised from ethanol, (1.510 g, 30%), m.p. $278-80^\circ$; giving purple colouration with ferric chloride. Its mixed m.p. with the authentic 2,6-dimethyl-4-hydroxyquinoline³ prepared from *p*-toluidine and ethyl acetoacetate was found to be the same. However, its 4-chloroquinoline derivative with phosphorous oxychloride was prepared and the ir spectra of both were examined.